

AKSIAL-SIMMETRIK TORTISHISH MAYDONI UCHUN PARAMETRIZATSIYA
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Annotatsiya: Jismning aylanishi, hatto bitta yo'nalishga bo'lsa ham, katta darajada Eynshteyn tenglamalarini murakkablashtiradi va ularning aniq yechimlarini olish katta qiyinchiliklarga duch keladi. Hozirgacha katta astrofizika qiziqishga ega bo'lgan tashqi yechimlardan faqat Kerr (Kerr, 1963) va Karter (Karter, 1968) metrikalari aniqlangan. Ular xususiy yechimlar bo'lib va maxsus turdagi manbaga to'g'ri keladi. Ular mos ravishda aylanadigan zaryadsiz yoki zaryadlangan qora o'ralarning tortishish maydoni bilan bog'liq (Karter, 1971; Xoking, Ellis, 1977). Mumkin bo'lgan aniq yechimlar aylanuvchi jismning fizik modeliga asos bo'lib xizmat qilish uchun hali aniqlanmagan. Manbaning bir o'q bilan aylanishining barqaror holat tabiati kvadratik shaklning aksial- simmetriyaga ega ekanligini va vaqtga bog'liq emasligini bildiradi. Shuning uchun mos sanoq sistemasi mavjud.

Kalit so'zlar: Qora tuynuklar, lagranj zichligi, Kerr, zaryadli zarra

Unda kordinatalarini t, r, θ, φ kiritish mumkin; bu metrikaning vaqtinchalik va aksial-simmetriyasini aniq aks ettiradi. Taxmin qilib aynan shu kordinatalar va sanoq sistemasi tizimlarining, umumiy holatda, ichki va tashqi hududlarida kvadratik formani shu tarzda ifodalash mumkin

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + \mathcal{A}(dt + \mathcal{B}\sin^2\theta d\varphi)^2 + \mathcal{D}dr^2 + \mathcal{E}d\theta^2 + \mathcal{F}\sin^2\theta d\varphi^2 \quad (1)$$

Noma'lum funksiyalar $\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{D}, \mathcal{E}, \mathcal{F}$ faqat r va φ ga bog'liq.

Xususan, Kerr metrikasi ham bu ko'rinishga keltiriladi (Boyer va Lindquist, 1967)

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + \frac{2Mr}{r^2 + a^2\cos^2\theta}(dt + a\sin^2\theta d\varphi)^2 + \frac{r^2 + a^2\cos^2\theta}{r^2 - 2Mr + a^2}dr^2 + (r^2 + a^2\cos^2\theta)d\theta^2 + (r^2 + a^2)\sin^2\theta d\varphi^2 \quad (2)$$

Bu yerda M jismning to'liq aylanish momenti bilan bog'liq doimiy kattalik.

Metrik tenzorning noldan farqli komponentalari shu formulalar bilan aniqlanadi.

$$\begin{aligned} g_{00} &= -(1 - \mathcal{A}), & g_{03} &= \mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}\sin^2\theta, & g_{11} &= \mathcal{D}, \\ g_{22} &= \mathcal{E}, & g_{33} &= (\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}^2\sin^2\theta + \mathcal{F})\sin^2\theta, & g &= -\mathcal{H}\mathcal{E}\mathcal{D}\sin^2\theta, \\ g^{00} &= -\frac{1}{\mathcal{H}}(\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}\sin^2\theta), & g^{03} &= \frac{1}{\mathcal{H}}\mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}, & g^{11} &= \frac{1}{\mathcal{D}} \\ g^{22} &= \frac{1}{\mathcal{E}}, & g^{33} &= \frac{1}{\mathcal{H}\sin^2\theta}(1 - \mathcal{A}), & \mathcal{H} &\equiv \mathcal{A}\mathcal{B}^2\sin^2\theta + \mathcal{F}(1 - \mathcal{A}) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Bu topilganlarni endi taqqoslab ko'ramiz.

Kerr metrikasida : $\mathcal{A} = \frac{2Mr}{\Sigma}, \mathcal{B} = a, \mathcal{D} = \Sigma/\Delta, \mathcal{E} = \Sigma, \mathcal{F} = (r^2 + a^2)^2$

Schwarzschild : $\mathcal{A} = \frac{2Mr}{\Sigma}, \mathcal{B} = 0, \mathcal{D} = \Sigma/\Delta, \mathcal{E} = \Sigma, \mathcal{F} = (r^2 + a^2)^2$

Kerr-Newman metrikasida : $\mathcal{A} = 1 - \frac{\Delta - a^2 \sin^2 \theta}{\Sigma}$, $\mathcal{B} = \Delta - r^2 - a^2$, $\mathcal{D} = \Sigma / \Delta$, $\mathcal{E} = 1 / \Sigma$, $\mathcal{F} = -\left(\frac{2r^2 a^2 - a^4}{\Sigma}\right)$

Agar hosilalarga belgilash kiritsak kristofel simvollarining noldan farqi komponentalari pastdagi formulalar bilan aniqlanadi.

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_{01}^0 &= \frac{1}{2\mathcal{H}} (\mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B} \mathcal{B}' \sin^2 \theta - \mathcal{F} \mathcal{A}'), & \Gamma_{00}^1 &= -\frac{\mathcal{A}'}{2\mathcal{D}}, \\ \Gamma_{02}^0 &= \frac{1}{2\mathcal{H}} [(\dot{\mathcal{B}} \sin \theta + 2\mathcal{B} \cos \theta) \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B} \sin \theta - \mathcal{F} \dot{\mathcal{A}}], \\ \Gamma_{00}^2 &= -\frac{\dot{\mathcal{A}}}{2\mathcal{H}}, & \Gamma_{13}^0 &= \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{2\mathcal{H}} [\mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B}^2 \mathcal{B}' \sin^2 \theta + \mathcal{A} \mathcal{B} \mathcal{F}' - \mathcal{F} (\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B})'], \\ \Gamma_{23}^0 &= \frac{\sin^2 \theta}{2\mathcal{H}} [(\dot{\mathcal{B}} \sin \theta + 2\mathcal{B} \cos \theta) \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B}^2 \sin \theta + \mathcal{A} \mathcal{B} \dot{\mathcal{F}} - \mathcal{F} (\dot{\mathcal{A}} \mathcal{B})], \\ \Gamma_{03}^1 &= -\frac{\sin^2 \theta}{2\mathcal{D}} (\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B})', & \Gamma_{03}^2 &= \frac{\sin \theta}{2\mathcal{E}} [(\dot{\mathcal{A}} \mathcal{B}) \sin \theta + 2\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B} \cos \theta], \\ \Gamma_{01}^3 &= \frac{1}{2\mathcal{H}} [(\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B})' - \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B}'], & \Gamma_{11}^1 &= \frac{\mathcal{D}'}{2\mathcal{D}}, & \Gamma_{12}^1 &= \frac{\dot{\mathcal{D}}}{2\mathcal{D}}, \\ \Gamma_{02}^3 &= \frac{1}{2\mathcal{H}} [(\dot{\mathcal{A}} \mathcal{B}) - \mathcal{A}^2 \dot{\mathcal{B}} + 2(1 - \mathcal{A}) \mathcal{A} \mathcal{B} \cot \theta], \\ \Gamma_{22}^1 &= -\frac{\mathcal{E}'}{2\mathcal{D}}, & \Gamma_{33}^1 &= -\frac{\sin^2 \theta}{2\mathcal{D}} [(\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B}^2)' \sin^2 \theta + \mathcal{F}'] \\ \Gamma_{11}^2 &= \frac{\dot{\mathcal{D}}}{2\mathcal{E}}, & \Gamma_{22}^2 &= \frac{\dot{\mathcal{E}}}{2\mathcal{E}}, & \Gamma_{12}^2 &= \frac{\mathcal{E}'}{2\mathcal{E}}, \\ \Gamma_{33}^2 &= -\frac{1}{2\mathcal{E}} [(\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B}^2) \sin^4 \theta + 4\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B}^2 \sin^3 \cos \theta + \dot{\mathcal{F}} \sin^2 \theta + 2\mathcal{F} \sin \theta \cos \theta], \\ \Gamma_{13}^3 &= \frac{1}{2\mathcal{H}} [(\mathcal{A}' \mathcal{B}^2 + 2\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B} \mathcal{B}' - \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B} \mathcal{B}') \sin^2 \theta + (1 - \mathcal{A}) \mathcal{F}'], \\ \Gamma_{23}^3 &= \frac{1}{2\mathcal{H}} [(\dot{\mathcal{A}} \mathcal{B}^2 + 2\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B} \dot{\mathcal{B}} - \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B} \dot{\mathcal{B}}) \sin^2 \theta + 2\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B}^2 \sin \theta \cos \theta \\ &+ 2(1 - \mathcal{A}) (\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B}^2 \sin^2 \theta + \mathcal{F}) \cot \theta + (1 - \mathcal{A}) \dot{\mathcal{F}}] \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

Sanoq sistemaning aylanuvchi jism uchun kvadratik formasi quyidagi formulaga keltiriladi. Uning elementlarining murakkab xarakterni xarakterlaydi, ularning absolyut tezlanishi xamma joyda ortogonal $A = \text{const}$, giper yuzalarga mansub

$$\omega_0 = \omega_3 = 0, \quad \omega_1 = -\frac{\mathcal{A}'}{2(1 - \mathcal{A})}, \quad \omega_2 = -\frac{\dot{\mathcal{A}}}{2(1 - \mathcal{A})}$$

$$A_{0i} = A_{12} = 0, \quad A_{13} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{(\mathcal{A} \mathcal{B})' - \mathcal{A}^2 \mathcal{B}'}{(1 - \mathcal{A})^{3/2}} \sin^2 \theta \quad (4)$$

Sanoqli sistemaning aylanish tenzor elementlari noldan farqli.

Hozirgi kunda ko'pgina exprementlar mavjud, lekin qaysi nazariyaga tegishli ekani aniq emas. Bu topilgan parametrizatsiya orqali biz o'zimizga tegishli yechimga o'tishimiz mumkin. Bu topilgan umumiy parametrizatsiya orqali matematik programmada qo'llash juda oson. Bu yechimni dasturga yozib olamiz va beshta noma'lum funksiyalarni kiritish orqali bizga kerak bo'lgan yechimga o'tsak bo'ladi. Bizga ma'lum bo'lgan yechimlarga mos kelishi tekshirib ko'rildi.

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